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Impact of 5G mmWave Spectrum on Numerical Weather Forecasting: Emerging Challenges and Strategies

PhD Students: Behzad Golparvar, Shaghayegh Vosoughitabar,
and David Bazzett

PIs: Narayan Mandayam, Chung-Tse Michael Wu, Joseph Brodie,
and **Ruo-Qian (Roger) Wang**

[10.5281/zenodo.13937697](https://zenodo.org/record/13937697)

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Background

5G mmWave Network

- Gbps wireless bit-rates
- Low latency
- Improved reliability
- Support of Internet-of-Things (IoT) applications

Background

5G Radio Frequency Interference Concerns

Background

❑ 5G Radio Frequency Interference Concerns

- 23.8 GHz is vital for water vapor measurements in the atmosphere
- Weather prediction models rely on passive sensors of weather satellites
- AMSU/ATMS sensors operate at 23.8 GHz on weather satellites

ATMS on the satellites including NOAA-20, NOAA-21

AMSU on the satellites including NOAA-19, NOAA-18

Controversy issues

5G could mean less time to flee a deadly hurricane, heads of NASA and NOAA warn

They're suggesting people could die because we won't have enough evacuation time

By Sean Hollister | @StarFire2258 | May 23, 2019, 3:41pm EDT

Theverge.com: May 2019

NEWS · 22 NOVEMBER 2019

Global 5G wireless deal threatens weather forecasts

Meteorologists say international standards for wireless technology could degrade crucial satellite measurements of water vapour.

Nature: November 2019

No, 5G Won't Ruin Your Weather Forecasts

The FCC has gotten into a fight with NOAA about 5G disrupting weather forecasting nationwide. The result will likely save your weather forecasts, but it'll weaken 5G coverage.

By Sascha Segan May 23, 2019

Pcmag.com: May
2019

Questions and Objectives

- How much will 5G RFI impact the weather forecast accuracy?
- How will the impact vary from place to place?
- When will the impact become significant?

Image Credit: Milan Yogendrappa. (2020)

Image Credit: Wikipedia

Methodology

① Predict the 5G service demand growth for different regions

② Estimate the 5G base station distribution throughout the contiguous United States

③ Study the potential leaked power from a single base station and calculate aggregated RFI

④ Perturb real satellite observations by adding the aggregated RFI

⑤ Conduct weather forecast simulations using contaminated satellite observations

❑ 5G mmWave Service Demand Prediction

- **Assumption:** 5G subscription trend can be assumed similar to the broadband (internet) adoption [1]
- The Gompertz model is selected to forecast the deployment of new technologies

$$F(t) = b_1 \exp(-b_2 \exp(-b_3 t))$$

- t : time in year
- b_1, b_2, b_3 : model parameters

- September 2021 is reported as the start date of the n258 band deployment

Methodology

❑ 5G Base Station Spatial Distribution

- Demand per user: 100 Mbps/user
- Spectrum bandwidth (B): 500 MHz
- Using county-level datasets
- Only urban and metropolitan counties
- Spectral efficiency (η_{sp}) choices: 7, 15, 25 bit/s/Hz/RS

$$N_{BS} = \frac{\text{Total Demand}}{\eta_{sp} \times B}$$

Methodology

❑ RFI from a Single Base Station

$$P_{\text{RFI}}^S = P_{\text{Leaked}} + G_{\text{BS}} + G_{\text{AMSU-A}} - P_L$$

The leaked power to the weather sensing band from a single base station	Gain of the base station's antenna array	Gain of the AMSU-A receiver	
Function of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transmitted power • Filtering response 	Function of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antenna array of the base station • Orientations of the satellite's receiver and base station's transmitter 	Function of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antenna array of the receiver • Orientations of the satellite's receiver and base station's transmitter 	Function of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distance of the AMSU-A from Earth • Wavelength of the signal • Weather condition

- P_{RFI}^S : **Interference power received by the radiometer from a single BS**
- The current suggested limit for the protection of Earth exploration services is **-3 dBm**
- If the leaked power from a single base station (P_{Leaked}), operating in n258 band is considered **-3 dBm**:
 - P_{RFI}^S can vary in a range between **-330 dBW** and **-150 dBW [2]**

Parametric Study

$$P_{\text{RFI}}^S = -210 \text{ dBW to } -165 \text{ dBW}$$

$$\eta_{\text{sp}} = 7, 15, 25 \text{ bit/s/Hz/BS}$$

Methodology

❑ RFI Weighted Aggregation for Observations

Assumptions:

- All base stations within each county have the same spectral efficiency and transmission power level
- Base station spatial distribution within each county is assumed to be uniform
- Each observation is only affected by the RFI emitted from the base stations within the covered area of that observation

➤ δT_{obs} : 5G mmWave induced brightness temperature contamination

➤ k : Boltzmann constant

➤ B : channel bandwidth 270 MHz

$$P_{\text{RFI}}^T = \sum_{i \in \text{c.c}} \frac{A_{\text{cover}}^i}{A_{\text{county}}^i} N_{\text{BS}}^i P_{\text{RFI}}^S$$

$$\delta T_{\text{obs}} = \frac{P_{\text{RFI}}^T}{kB}$$

Methodology

❑ Numerical Experiment

- How much would 5G mmWave RFI impact a 12-hour weather forecasting of the Super Tuesday Tornado Outbreak?
- Second deadliest disaster in February in the US history with
 - ❑ 87 observed tornadoes
 - ❑ 57 casualties reported
 - ❑ \$1.2 billion property loss
- 12-hour forecasting simulation beginning at 12 UTC on Feb 05, 2008

❑ Simulation Model/Algorithm

- Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) Data Assimilation model (WRFDA)
- Built in WRF software data assimilation model
- The radiance data was collected from the AMSU instrument

Results

□ Aggregated RFI in terms of Brightness Temperature

- Level of contamination in Brightness Temperature – AMSU-A channel 1 @ 23.8 GHz
- 5G-induced noise in brightness temperature for $P_{\text{RFI}}^S = -175 \text{ dBW}$ and $\eta_{\text{SE}} = 15 \text{ bit/s/Hz/BS}$

Results

Forecast Simulation Results

- Forecast change for $P_{\text{RFI}}^S = -175$ dBW and $\eta_{\text{SE}} = 15$ bit/s/Hz/BS and Year=2040

Min = -10.7192, Max = 8.2139

Min = -0.6543, Max = 1.3179

Results

- Impact of RFI Level on Forecast Change

- Outdoor Base Stations ($\eta_{SE} = 15$ bit/s/Hz/BS)

Results

□ Impact Mechanism and Data Loss

- Observation Rejection
- Scattering Index is a function of brightness temperature at channel 1 (23.8 GHz)
- Reject if $SI > 3.0$

Conclusion

- Developed a framework to study the impact of the 5G mmWave deployment on numerical weather forecast accuracy
- If $P_{\text{RFI}}^S = -175$ dBW and $\eta_{SE} = 15$ bit/s/Hz/BS, 5G RFI has limited impact in the year 2025 but can result in an induced noise in brightness temperature up to 17 K in the year 2040
 - That level of RFI can significantly impact the 12-hour forecast of a severe weather event
 - Forecasting error of up to 10 mm in precipitation and 1.75 C in 2m temperature
- If $P_{\text{RFI}}^S = -200$ dBW, then there is no impact on forecasting errors even in 2040
- RFI can potentially lead to loss of some observations in WRFDA data assimilation algorithm

Mitigation and Future Steps

- ✓ Resource allocation for RFI reduction (Majumdar et al. 2022 IEEE FNWF conference)
- ✓ Filtenna transceiver design for RFI reduction (a paper and talk by Vosoughitabar et al. on Thursday 9:30 AM)
- ✓ Data assimilation and weather forecast using more advanced packages such as UFS (Unified Forecast System)
- ✓ Assessing 5G RFI using an experimental setup and real measurement
- ✓ Developing statistical RFI detection methods and use for improving weather prediction algorithms

THANK YOU

Q&A
QUESTIONS &
ANSWERS